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Ageing Population: An Implication for Nurses

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Abstract:

Ageing is a universal phenomenon that is obvious as well as inevitable. It is a process that begins from conception and continues for as long as we live. The concept of ageing is multifaceted. Though old age is not a disease, it is the phase of retrograde biological process in growth and development which leads to decreased powers of survival and adjustment. In the care of the elderly, the severely impaired or dependent elderly will need range of professional care as well as with their families. Caring for the elderly by nurses is very challenging, time consuming and tasking. In the process of creating adequate services, home care and institutional service are complementary and multi directional and care of such patients need shared responsibility of both families and professional service provider. It is recommended that Nurses should advocate for the elderly since it is expected that social services would be overwhelmed by the growing ageing population.

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Introduction

Ageing is a universal phenomenon that is obvious as well as inevitable. According to UN projections, there will be 1.2 billion old people in the globe in 2025, with 71 percent of them anticipated to live in developing countries. The "Old" Old (those aged 80 and up) will grow twice as quickly as the 60-plus age group between 1950 and 2025. In these circumstances, we have two key challenges: providing older people with possibilities for independence, health, production, and protection while maintaining societal economic prosperity.

Concept of Ageing

Ageing is defined as changes that significantly decrease the probability of survival caused by processes within the individual that are universal, inevitable and irreversible. It is a multidimensional process of physical, psychological and social accumulation of change in a person over time (Abanyam, 2012). It is a process that begins from conception and continues for as long as we live. Individual age at different rates and their ageing experience is unique and there are generalizations which can be observed for each of the body systems (Boswell, 2012).

Ageing may be "universal" that is (age changes that all people share); "probabilistic ageing" (age changes that may happen to some but not all people as they grow older); "social/cultural ageing" (expectations of how people should act as they grow older); "biological ageing" (an organism's physical state as it ages); "proximal ageing" (age-based effects that comes about because of factors in the recent past); "distal ageing" (age-based differences that can be traced back to a cause in early life (Ali, et al., 2018).

Old age is a significant stage in life and normally related to life expectancy of given area, hence the conditions and the needs of the elderly becomes imperative. Preparation for old age cannot be over emphasized. Ageing does not only refer to an individual's chronological or physiological age, but also the attitudes, viewpoints and belief towards ageing. The way nations or individuals define who is considered an elderly has to do, or could be as a result of elements of social construction both at local and global level. The concept of who is an elderly comes as a result of interactions among individuals in the society. As far as assumptions and expectations on ageing is concerned, each culture holds its own perspectives or view-points on ageing, which in all, is part of socialization. Some define the elderly in measure of physical health while others define it in terms of chronological age.

According to the WHO, most developed countries have accepted the chronological age of 65 years and above as the definition of an elderly person, for this is the age within which an individual could start receiving pension benefits. At the moment, there is no United Nations numerical standard criterion to refer to an elderly population, though it has agreed on the 60 and above as cut off point in reference to older population (United Nations, 2017). Ageing can be categorized into three groups such as; "the young old" ages from (60- 74years); "the middle old" (75-84years) and "the older old (oldest)" (85years and above) (Cadmus, et al., 2017).

The concept of ageing is multifaceted. This is because its in-depth description or explanation covers diverse areas of human development. There are chronological, biological, psychological and social, functional dimensions of ageing (Luhmann & Hawkley, 2016). The chronological dimension describes the number of years that have slipped away since one's birth while the biological explains the status of vital organs of the body as an individual

advances in age. The psychological dimension focuses on individuals' ability to adapt to environmental demands/challenges while social dimension sheds light on how an individual conforms to written and unwritten norms, roles expected of him/her by the society in which he/she operates. The functional dimension measures how effective an individual is in physical and social environment when compared with other people within his/ her age bracket (Luhmann & Hawkey, 2016).

Ageing process is a biological reality which has its own dynamics largely beyond human control. It is subject to the constructions by which each society makes sense of old age. As observed so far, in the developed world, chronological age plays a paramount role. The age of 60 or 65 roughly equivalent to retirement ages in most developed countries is said to be the beginning of old age. In many parts of the developing world, chronological age has little or no importance in the meaning of old age. Socially constructed meanings of elderly are more significant such as the roles assigned to the elderly in some cases. The loss of the roles accompanying some physical declines is significant in defining old age in many developing countries. Thus, in contrast to the chronological milestones which mark life stages in the developed world, WHO (2019) however posited that old age in many developing countries is seen to begin at the point when active contributions to life is no longer possible.

The Ageing Population

The population of old people throughout the world is increasing at a very rapid rate (Population Reference Bureau, 2011). The most rapid increase is taking place in the developing world with Africa alone projected to have between 204 and 210 million old people by the year 2050. This unprecedented rise in the number old people presents fundamental socio-economic difficulties (Olaleye, 2011). Nigeria with a population of 140.8 million people (NPC 2006) is the most populated nation in Africa and the ninth in the world (UN, 2005). Life expectancy at birth stands at 57.6 years (NPC, 2008). The population growth rate (2000 – 2005) is 2.5% with 5.6% of the total population aged 60 and above. As the most populous country in Africa, Nigeria currently has the highest number of aged or elderly people in Africa Population Reference Bureau (PRB, 2011) with the largest population in Africa and the ninth in the world, it is estimated that by year 2025, the population of Nigeria aged 60 and above will constitute 6 percent of the entire population as projected by (UN population Division, 2005).

Old age is not a disease; it is the phase of retrograde biological process in growth and development which leads to decreased powers of survival and adjustment. The World Health Organization has always designated as "Elderly" people aged 65 years and above. In 1980, the United Nations defined 60 years as the age of transition of people (U.N, 2004). The elderly make up an increasing proportion of the population in developed world and this demographic transition also affects some developing countries. Generally the elderly are at increased risk of disease, disability, social and financial deprivation compared to the younger generation in the same population (National Council on Ageing and the elderly (NCAOP), 2005). An increase in the number of the elderly will lead to increased demands on health and support services including elderly care residential services and acute health service (McCormacks, 2004).

Characteristics and Challenges of the Ageing Population

The elderly population is increasing in all countries of the world (World Population Ageing, 2013). This is due to several factors including decline in fertility, improvement in public

health and increase in life expectancy. The decline in fertility is brought about by a more widespread acceptability of family planning, while increase in life expectancy is attributable to improved medical care brought about by technological advancement (Asiyanbola, 2005). As there are regional differences between developed and developing nations of the world, so there are differences among regions globally in the number of older persons (United Nations, 2002; Okumagba, 2011).

Okumagba (2011) observes that in developed regions of the world, about one-fifth of the population was aged 60 and above in the year 2000 and that it is expected that by 2050, their population would have reached one-third. However, in developing regions of the globe, 8 percent of their population is over 60 years of age and it is equally expected that by 2050, those within the age group will reach 20 percent of the population (United Nations, 2002). Comparatively, U.S Census Bureau (2009) projects that the number of people older than 65 will double to 14 percent from 7 percent of the world's population in the next 30 years, thus, rising to 1.4 billion by 2040 from about 506 million in 2008. This rapid rise in the elderly population according to the U.S Census Bureau (2009), is taking place in developing countries where increase in the number of people aged 65 years and older is more than double the rate in developed nations. The U.S. Census Bureau (2009) observes that 313 million or 62 percent, of the world's elderly lived in developing countries, and their population is projected to rise to more than one billion, 76 percent of the world's 65-and-over population by 2040.

Nigeria which has a population of approximately 150 million (NPC, 2006) is ranked the most populated African nation and the ninth in the world (UN, 2004). Various published demographic projections showed that the proportion of elderly persons in Nigeria is on the increase. According to the 1991 Population Census, there were 4,598,114 persons aged 60 and above in Nigeria. This was about 5.2 percent of the total national population of 88,992,220. The number of the elderly is projected to have increased to around 5 million by the year 2000 (NPC, 1998). In the 2006 Population and Housing Census in Nigeria, 6,987,047 persons making up 4.9 percent of the population were aged 60 years and above. Even though there is a slight decrease in the percentage of the elderly population from the 1991 census, there is an observable increase in the absolute number of the elderly population. With regards to sex composition of the elderly national population, there were more males than females in all age groups 60+, only 44 percent were females.

The first sign of ageing begins with the skin which becomes drier, thinner and has elastic wrinkles, visible blood vessels and pocket of fat under the skin appear as irrefutable evidence of the passage of time (Levant et al, 2015). Merrill and Verbrugge (2011) also revealed that with time pockets of fat settle on various parts of the body most noticeable around the abdomen, but also on the upper arms, the buttocks, eyelids and double chin, bones become fragile and more easily broken and difficult to heal. The Muscles loose power and become atrophy while joints stiffen or wear out, circulation slows down, blood pressure rises and because the lungs hold less oxygen the elderly has less energy, reaction to stimuli is slower and there is less resistance to illness. There are difficulties to fall asleep and remaining asleep and vision, hearing and sense of smell became less acute (Levant, et al., 2015).

Disability significantly affects quality of life in old age though it is considered to be consequences of the normal ageing process; they are often caused by chronic diseases which the elderly are at risk (Szucs, 2001). There seems to be a problem with providing the

appropriate care for these disabilities for this segment of the population yet the population is growing rapidly in both developed and developing countries (Vitalianie, et al., 2003).

The lack of health care for senior citizens is a crucial problem with the assumption that provision of healthcare services has always been adequate. This assumption is wrong as recent research has shown that Medical care is not easily accessible. This is because the geographical distance to get to these services makes it difficult, if not impossible for many the elderly to access, particularly in the rural areas (Nussbaum, 2003). Hence, their health needs still has to be met by visiting traditional medical men and herbalists. At the family level care services provided do not adequately meet the needs of the old persons. Diminishing economic power has hindered the willing family members. However these changes demand that governments, the private sector, nongovernmental organizations and the civil society in general be prepared to deal with them, bearing in mind the special needs of the people.

Nevertheless, most elderly persons cannot afford quality medical care. A survey of more than 3,200 senior citizens found that many people would be prepared to pay for high quality elderly care, while wanting a safety net for those who cannot afford to pay (O' Neil, 2010). The care and support by the family and community that were taken for granted in the past have stopped, because of changes in the society associated with urbanization and development in general (Ting & Woo, 2009).

In some communities in Africa instead of relaxing and enjoying old age, the senior citizens are obliged, once again, to take up the responsibility of caring for children and young adults suffering from HIV/AIDs related problems or migrate. Apart from the children, old people are the social group most vulnerable to the numerous ills facing Africa, poverty, food insecurity, civil strife, armed conflict, violence and inadequate social welfare services.

National Council on Ageing (2020) suggest that sensory loss will make any elderly person to forget something that is immediate, but may sometimes remember things in the far past. Most elderly are afraid to being hospitalized, for they had already assumed hospital to be dying places (Lecovich, 2008). Humphries, et al (2008) also observed that living patterns are changing as urbanization has resulted in many elderly people living alone in rural areas. This occurs, when their children might have migrated to the urban centre, in search for greener pasture. Economic pressure and changing social values mean that many families are either unable or unwilling to care for the elderly. The contributions that elderly people make to the family are seldom acknowledged and programmes designed to support families fail to take into account the valuable role that old people do play (Cadmus, et al., 2017).

Common Diseases associated with the Ageing Population

As a person ages, the immune system weakens, organs begin to deteriorate and body becomes susceptible to variety of diseases. Some of the common diseases of ageing are

Arthritis: - This refers to a variety of inflammatory joint disorders including osteoarthritis, rheumatoid arthritis and gout. Symptoms are pain, swelling of the joint and difficulty in moving. Arthritis is the commonest problem ageing in humans (Iwasaki & Jones, 2008)

Alzheimer's Diseases: - This is the disorder of the brain, including the death of brain cells which affects brain functioning and cognitive ability. It prevents with minor memory loss and confusion and progresses to more severe cognitive and physical impairment. It is the major cause of frailty which leads to falls in aged persons

Cardiovascular Diseases (CVD): - refers to a variety of disorders, including pericarditis (inflammation of the pericardium), atherosclerosis (fatty deposit in the arteries) hypertension (High Blood Pressure) etc. Symptoms include chest pain, breathlessness, dizziness, palpitations, stroke, severe headache etc.

Parkinson 's Disease: - This is a disorder of the nervous system manifesting in tremors, slow movements, speech impairment, dementia and difficulty in walking.

Pneumonia: - An inflammation of the lungs caused by a bacterial, viral or fungal infection. Pneumonia present in cold symptoms, shivers, blood stained sputum, headache, cough, vomiting and chest pain.

Stroke: - This is a condition in which a blood vessel leading to the brain gets clogged or bursts, thus denying part of the brain blood flow and oxygen and eventually killing the cells in that part of the brain. Stroke presents with numbness, weakness speech impairment, severe headache, dizziness and vision problems.

Caring for the Ageing Population

Caring for an elderly person does not come without challenges for those who give or practice it either by requiring their substances, presence, touch or attention to listen to the elderly (Faronbi, et al 2017). Some elderly persons are active right up until they succumb to natural causes of death, while some experience health problems for years. All elderly persons have a host of daily living issues to contend with. Finances, movement, house chores, etc are some of the "Activities of Daily Living" that become more difficult as one gets older.

The elderly consequently face a broad range of medical and physical needs that require assistance and supervision on a temporary or full-time basis, depending on their needs. Knowing their care needs will help health professionals to understand how to help them or find someone who can assist (Bass & Noelker, 2007). In other words, the social and medical programs and facilities intended for the care and maintenance of the aged or the elderly people is simply the meaning of the concept of 'Care' for the elderly as operationalized in this study.

In general terms, those who feel concerned to care for the elderly are potential Elderly Health professionals. It could be government, NGOs, Nurses in Adult Homes, individuals in the society who are not relations of the elderly, spouses of the elderly, adult children of the elderly (sons and daughters), daughters-in-law and grandchildren.

Traditionally, the care for the elderly in Nigeria has been within the extended family system (Faronbi, et al., 2017). They are cared for by their children, daughters-in-law and other extended family members like grandchildren. Researchers have found that within families there is a hierarchy of health professionals providing care to older persons (Horowitz, 2005). Their spouses are first expected to assume care-giving responsibilities if they do not have limitations of their own that might prevent them from providing the care, followed by an adult-daughter or daughter in-law (Merrill, 2003; Peters-Davis, et al., 2009; Stephens & Franks, 2009).

It is important for nurses to have adequate knowledge on the basic needs of the elderly than the rest of the population (Okoye & Asa, 2011). This is necessary because these needs must be met every day for the elderly to be able to live independently for as long as possible and nurses would be able to help the elderly meet these needs without compromising their health and safety. Nurses need to have adequate knowledge of taking care of the elderly.

According to Redmond, et al. (2008), ageism has been found to negatively affect the health care services that older persons receives, both implicitly through unfair resource allocation by stakeholders and explicitly by providing offensive and poor quality treatment. Maltreatment of the elderly has been identified in facilities for continuing care such as nursing home, residential care, hospitals and day care facilities. The spectrum of these within institution may be related to any of the following, the provision of care for example resistance to changes in geriatric medicine, erosion of individuality of care, inadequate nutrition and deficient nursing care problem with staffing, poor interaction/communication and poor environment, and organization policies – bureaucratic or unsympathetic attitudes toward residents (National Council on Ageing, 2020).

Esopenko and Levine (2015) stipulated that in the care of the elderly, the severely impaired and dependent elderly will need range of professional care as well as with their families so in the process of creating adequate services, home care and institutional service are complementary and multi directional and care of such patients need shared responsibility of both families and professional service provider.

Problems Associated with Care of the Ageing Population

Nurses experience different health problems when taking care of the elderly. These problems results from the responsibilities and task involved in caring for the elderly. The daily tasks involved include bathing, dressing, feeding, lifting, turning him or her in bed, cooking, shopping, paying of bills, running errands, giving medicine, keeping him or her company, providing emotional support (Okoye & Asa, 2011). All these help can be time consuming and emotionally, physically and psychologically draining and may expose the health worker to stress, risk of diseases, neglect of one self, poor health and depression (Donatelle, 2011).

According to Donatelle (2011), some nurses get easily irritated when taking care of the elderly than when taking care of other age groups because of the daily task involved. The stress impact negatively on the health of the health workers or cause the health workers to be physically or verbally aggressive towards the care receiver. Studies have shown that one reason for elderly abuse and neglect is caregiver's stress (Lecovich, 2008). It is also very common for health workers to get angry, feel frustrated, guilt, isolated, unhappy in marriage, anxiety, depressed, diminished socially, loss of self-esteem from time to time and dissatisfaction with life.

According to Okoye and Asa (2011) feeling guilty about all the things that are not going on right is the cardinal feature of nurses' experience. Stress of caregivers has been shown to be influenced by many factors which include the attitude of the health professional or care giver (Okoye & Asa, 2011).

Okoye and Asa (2011) in a study of leisure and distress in care givers for elderly patients revealed that nurses taking care of the elderly are more likely to neglect their own needs because care of the elderly is time consuming and tasking. They may not recognize or may ignore the signs of illness, exhaustion or depression that they are experiencing. Frustration is also one of the feelings that may occur as a result of taking care of the elderly. This arises out of trying to change an uncontrollable condition in taking care of the elderly especially Alzheimer's disease or other kinds of dementia (Alzheimer's, Society, 2009).

Nurses taking care of the elderly are also at risk of contracting diseases because of the closeness and commitment needed in the care of the elderly (Lecovich, 2008). Accordingly,

Merril and Verbrugge, (2011) common diseases that affect the elderly that can be transmitted to the caregivers are Tuberculosis, HIV/AIDS among others.

Conclusion

Ageing can result in a variety of health problems. With the elderly accounting for 12% of the world's population and expected to rise to almost 22% by 2050, It's critical to identify the obstacles that people experience as they age and to recognize that there are preventive actions you (or a loved one) can take to put yourself (or a loved one) on a path to healthy ageing. As a result, nurses have a responsibility to act independently of the environment in order to promote quality of life and active ageing.

As a result, organizations concerned, as well as society as a whole, should work to create an aged-friendly environment that can provide useful knowledge to the old. Nurses need to wake up to the impending issues of health care and fill in the gaps for our community's elderly.

Being aware of age-related psychological changes, such as reduced level of vision and hearing, slower processing and reaction time, will allow caregivers to properly manage health risks and make well informed decisions. Such enlightenment could help maintain the physical and mental health of the ageing population.

The aforementioned preventative levels of care can help with quality of care and active ageing. Primary prevention for the elderly assures not only the prevention of death but also the promotion of health in old age. Nurses should advocate for the elderly since it is expected that social services would be overwhelmed by the growing ageing population. Qualified personnel should be hired by health facilities to conduct evaluations on the projected new geriatric population. The care of the elderly is being harmed by a "nursing shortage," and nurses are "too busy" to assist elderly patients with basic care. This attitude must change.

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